

Perceived Patients Satisfaction Toward Quality of Nursing Care in Selected Governmental Teaching Hospitals (Nyala, Zalingei and, Geneina), Darfur States, Sudan: Across-section study

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Abstract

Background: Patients satisfaction is crucial for assessing care quality within the healthcare system, and satisfaction with nursing services significantly impacts overall patient satisfaction in hospitals.

Objective: To assess the patients satisfaction toward the quality of nursing care in selected teaching governmental hospitals in Sudan.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional hospital base study. conducted in three governmental teaching hospitals from 2022 to 2023. The study included 700 patients selected by total coverage technique. Data were collected through face-to-face interview using Patient Satisfaction with Nursing Care Quality Questionnaire (PSNCQQ). The data were analyzed using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (Version 24).

Results: The results revealed that the overall mean score of patients satisfaction with quality of nursing care was very good ($M = 2.57$, $SD = \pm 0.877$). There was significant association between (marital status, educational level, residence, and previous hospitalization) with patients satisfaction at P - value ($p < .05$).

Conclusion: The study concluded that the overall level of patients satisfaction with the quality of nursing care was a very good level. There was significant association between marital status, occupation, educational level, residence, and previous hospitalization with patients satisfaction.

Recommendations: Improving the quality of nursing care should be focus more on educated patients when providing quality of nursing care. Further studies should be conducted concerning patients satisfaction with nursing care provided in all hospitals.

KEYWORDS: Patients, satisfaction, Quality of Nursing care.

1. INTRODUCTION:

"Patient satisfaction is crucial for evaluating the quality of care. Nurses play an essential role in providing high-quality nursing care, which significantly impacts overall hospital satisfaction." ⁽¹⁾. Patient satisfaction with nursing care is an essential factor explaining patient perception of service quality. According to O'Connor et al., the patient perspective is increasingly seen as a meaningful indicator of the quality of health services and may represent an important perspective ⁽²⁾. Competent nursing care is essential for surgical patients to ensure they receive safe and patient-centered treatment. The quality of nursing care can be measured by assessing patients' level of satisfaction, and patient satisfaction increases through proper nursing care ⁽³⁾. In addition, Patients' satisfaction with their care can lead to patients' loyalty and trust: satisfied patients are loyal and more inclined to return to the same hospital or healthcare provider in the future to suggest them to other relatives and friends ⁽³⁾. Total Quality Management(TQM) encompasses professional expertise, competency, and use of appropriate technology, the patient's perception about the type and level of care they have received, today's consumer-oriented healthcare markets, a patient-centered measure of satisfaction with the quality of nursing care received is a component of hospital quality management systems ⁽⁴⁾.

Regarding the definition of the term "patient satisfaction" in the healthcare context, the literature cannot agree. Patient satisfaction is defined as a patient-reported outcome measure in the Donabedian's quality measurement model, while patient-reported experience can be used to measure other constructs and processes ⁽⁵⁾.

Patient satisfaction is a patient's subjective assessment of their cognitive and emotional response to the interaction between their expectations of ideal nursing care and their perception of the practical nursing care ⁽⁶⁾. The definition of perception is the method used to understand or think about someone or something patients' perceptions often refer to their perceptions of the services they received and the outcomes of their treatment ⁽⁷⁾.

PROBLEM STATEMENT:

It is essential to evaluate patient satisfaction with nursing care to understand patients' needs and to plan and implement appropriate nursing interventions. Many recent studies have aimed to assess patient satisfaction with nursing care, with high levels of satisfaction reported in research conducted in Iraq, Brazil, and Egypt ⁽⁸⁾. Additionally,

the overall level of patient satisfaction with nursing care was 69% in Iran, 67% in Kenya, and 33% in Ghana ⁽⁹⁾. On the contrary, a study conducted in India revealed that most hospitalized patients had negative perceptions regarding nursing care ⁽⁸⁾. Specifically, surgical patients often experience anxiety and stress related to their surgery ⁽¹⁰⁾. Consequently, They have high expectations for nursing care and require extensive information about their conditions, procedures, treatment options, and post-surgery expectations ⁽¹⁰⁾. Many factors prevent nurses from carrying out quality nursing care, such as a poor working environment, inadequate drug supply, nurses' shortage, increasing patient admissions, poor leadership, and a lack of equipment and materials. These factors lead to low-quality nursing care ⁽¹¹⁾. The main problem in Sudan is that their no previous studies on the quality of nursing care provided to surgical patients, despite the importance of the nursing services in a health care system.

JUSTIFICATIONS:

The delivery of nursing care comprises a significant portion of all health services provided by healthcare organizations. It is crucial to examine patients' perceptions about satisfaction and experiences to identify areas of satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Patient satisfaction is an essential measure for evaluating the performance of the healthcare system ⁽¹²⁾. Measuring patient satisfaction is more challenging than other performance evaluation criteria in the health care system. Despite the importance of the nursing services in a health care system, there is lack of previous studies on patients satisfaction toward the quality of nursing care provided to surgical patients in Sudan. Therefore, the aim of this study is to assess the perception of patients satisfaction toward the quality of nursing care for patients admitted to general surgical wards.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

General objective:

The general objective of this study is to assess the perception of patients satisfaction toward the quality of nursing care for patients admitted to general surgical wards.

Specific objectives:

The specific objectives will be:

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1. To assess the level of patients' satisfaction with overall nursing care provided to them.
2. To investigate the association between sociodemographic characteristics and their patients' satisfaction.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

What are the level of patients satisfaction about the quality of nursing care provided in general surgical wards ?

Hypothesis

Ho= There is no the association between sociodemographic characteristics and their patients' satisfaction.

H1=There is the association between sociodemographic characteristics and their patients' satisfaction.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Study design

A descriptive, cross-sectional hospital based study was conducted during the period (Jan 2022 - Jan 2023).

2.2 Study area

The study was conducted in three selected main governmental teaching hospitals in central Darfur state, South Darfur state and West Darfur state (Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina Teaching Hospitals).

Darfur region lies in western Sudan, which is approximately 493,180 km² in area and has a population of nearly six million. It comprises of the states of North, West, South, East, and Central Darfur ⁽¹³⁾.

2.2.1. Zalingei Teaching Hospital:

The Zalingei Teaching Hospital is one of the biggest hospitals in central Darfur state and is which established in 1956. Located in the city center, the west of the old mosque and south of the big market. It has an area of about 2000m². It consists of the Outpatient department, Radiology department, laboratory and blood bank department, Obstetric and Gynecological department, pediatrics department, operation and ICU department, Nutrition department, and General medical-surgical wards for male and female patients. It has 246 beds, 54 beds in the surgical ward 131 nurses providing

nursing care and 53 Nurses rotated for the male and female Medical -Surgical wards. The information mentioned above was collected from statistics department in these hospital.

2.2.2. Nyala Teaching Hospital:

The Nyala teaching hospital is located in central Nyala city, it is a tertiary and referral health facility that offers medical and surgical services referral from hospitals or clinics all around the state, It consists of many clinics and many wards such as emergency department medicals, obstetrics and gynecology, pediatrics, and surgical wards, nursery unit, two intensive care units. The total nurses worked in two shifts, 8 hours morning shift and 16 hours. Afternoon and night shift staff the total number of nurses is 128 and 30 nurses provide care for patients admitted to male and female surgical wards. The information mentioned above was collected from statistics department in these hospital.

2.2.3. Geneina Teaching Hospital:

Geneina Teaching Hospital is located in the capital of West Darfur State at Geneina town, established in 1963 to teach medical and nursing students, train medical and nursing staff, and provide medical services to the community of West Darfur State and neighboring Chad and Central African Republic. It composed of eight wards (Male and Female Surgical wards, Male and Female medical wards, General pediatric ward, pediatric nutrition rehabilitation ward and obstetrical and gynecological ward consist of many units such as hemodialysis unit, dental unit, diabetic unit, and ICU unit. Surgical wards number of nurse = Female =12, Male =12 Total = 24 nurses. Number of bed = Male 28bed, Female = 28bed, Total = 56beds The information mentioned above was collected from statistics department in these hospital.

2.3 Study population:

All patients, who admitted to the general surgical wards of Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina Teaching Hospitals.

2.3.1 Inclusion criteria:

The patients recruited in the study included those who:

- Adult patients of age group 18 years and above admitted in surgical wards in Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina teaching Hospitals.
- Has had surgery performed while under general or spinal anesthesia.

- Were in stable general condition postoperative fully conscious.
- Stayed in the ward for two or more days postoperatively.
- Who were consented to be included in the study.

2.3.2 Exclusion criteria:

Patients who were excluded from the study included those:

- Who were not operated on?
- Who did not consent to participate?
- Who are able to communicate?
- Who with burn injury or diabetic septic foot?

2.4 Sample size and sampling technique:

2.4.1 Sample size:

The researcher was selecting the sample for all patients who fulfil the above criteria in surgical wards at Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina Teaching Hospitals.

2.4.2 Sampling technique:

The study involved all patients who admitted to the general surgical wards of Zalingei, Nyala and Geneina Teaching Hospitals.

2.5 Variables under the study:

A variable is a characteristic or quality that takes on different values for example it varies from one person or object to another.

2.5.1 Independent variables:

The independent variables includes (age, gender, educational level, occupation, residence and, previous hospitalization).

2.5.2 Dependent variables

Dependent variable means the variable hypothesized to depend on or be caused by another variable (the independent variable). in this study, the dependent variables were patients satisfaction regarding quality of nursing care.

2.6 Data collection instrument

The data collection instrument consist of two sections as follow:

2.6.1 Section one

The first part of the tool has six questions related to demographic characteristics of the patients such as age, gender, educational level, occupation, residence, and, previous hospitalization.

2.6.2 Section two

The second part of the tool is **Patient Satisfaction with Nursing Care Quality Questionnaire (PSNCQQ)** that has nineteen questions of patients satisfaction of a 5-point Likert-type scale. The PSNCQQ can be incorporated into existing hospital quality monitoring systems to monitor patient satisfaction. In addition, the PSNCQQ can be used as an evidence-based indicator given its contribution to the patient care process as a result variable, to evaluate changes in departmental and institutional processes. This feedback provides useful information to nurse administrators ⁽⁴⁾.

2.6 2.1. Scoring of the patients satisfaction

The **Scoring of the patients satisfaction** based on responses of a 5-point Likert-type scale that ranged from one to five (1 = excellent, 2 = very good, 3 = good, 4 = fair, 5 = poor). The total possible scores range from 19–95 points. Lower total scores indicate greater satisfaction with nursing care and higher total scores indicate lower satisfaction with nursing care ⁽⁴⁾.

2.8 Validity of tools

Study tools were designed after an in-depth review of the literature. The draft was appraised by the supervisor. A subsequent review with three expert committees to judge the appropriateness, accuracy, and representiveness of the instruments. firstly the tools were revised by institutional review board of AL Neelain University. Secondly the tools were revised by three related academic staff; one surgeon from a surgical department; one nursing expert, and one statistician to test the clarity, feasibility and applicability of instruments.

2.9 Reliability of tools

The study reliability analysis was undertaken to measure the consistency, stability, and repeatability of the instrument. A pilot study was done on 70 patients (10%) of the total sample to check the reliability of the instrument. we find that the reliability of the questionnaire is 92%, which indicates the excellent credibility of the participants in their answers to the questions of the questionnaire, while the stability coefficient is defined as the degree of stability of the results based on the analysis of the questionnaire if we take another sample, there is measured by the squared root of the

Cronbach coefficient alpha, and this (96%) indicates the strength of the stability of the results of the sample members participating in the questionnaire.

2.10 Ethical clearance of the study

The researcher followed many steps to accomplish the ethical clearance.

- Ethical approval was obtained from the research ethics committee and institutional review board of faculty of graduate studies and scientific research of Alneelain University.
- An official letters were taken from the ministry of health in Central Darfur State, South Darfur State, and West Darfur State. Then formal headed letter were sent to the managers of selected hospitals.
- Verbal informed consent had taken individually from each participant, after explanation of purpose, justification of study in clear and simple words. The name of the participant was not required serial number used instead. The complete autonomy participation was voluntary. The participant had the options to accept or reject and had the right to withdraw at any time. The data was confidential and kept for three years it was discharge after three years.

3. RESULTS

Out of 700 patients who participated in the study, more than half of them (55%) were male, and (25.1%) were belonged to the age group (18 - 24) years, and most of the participants (64.6%) were married. Additionally, the majority of the participants (26.4%) had a business, most of them (22.7%) had a Khalwa level of education, and half of them (50.0%) lived in urban areas. Furthermore, (41.2%) of them had not been admitted to the hospital before.

Section (1): Sociodemographic characteristics of Participants.

Figure (4.1) Frequency and percentage of gender in the study sample (n = 700).

Figure (4.2) Frequency and percentage of age in the study sample (n = 700).

Figure (4.3) Frequency and percentage of marital status in the study sample (n = 700).

Figure (4.4) Frequency and percentage of occupation in the study sample (n = 700).

Figure (4.5) Frequency and percentage of educational level in the study sample (n = 700).

Figure (4.6) Frequency and percentage of residence in the study sample (n = 700).

Figure (4.7) Frequency and percentage of previous hospitalization in the study sample (n = 700).

Section (2):

Table (4.1): Patients Satisfaction regarding quality of nursing care.

(N = 700)

Patient satisfaction		Excellent	Very good	Good	Fair	Poor	Total	Mean	SD
How clear and complete the nurse's explanations were about tests, treatments, and what to expect.	N	143	112	107	144	194	700	3.19	1.50
	%	20%	16%	15%	21%	28%	100%		
How well nurses explained and to prepare for tests and operations.	N	130	108	135	140	187	700	3.21	1.46
	%	19%	15%	19%	20%	27%	100%		
How the willingness of nurses to answer your questions.	N	239	175	164	87	35	700	2.29	1.20
	%	34%	25%	23%	12%	5%	100%		
How well nurses communicated with patients, families, and doctors.	N	309	129	149	75	38	700	2.15	1.25
	%	44%	18%	21%	11%	5%	100%		
How well the nurses kept them informed about your conditions and needs.	N	189	130	241	91	49	700	2.54	1.21
	%	27%	19%	34%	13%	7%	100%		
How much they were allowed to help in your care.	N	177	146	232	98	47	700	2.56	1.20
	%	25%	21%	33%	14%	7%	100%		
Were they given you courtesy, respect, friendliness and kindness?	N	320	104	162	78	36	700	2.15	1.26
	%	46%	15%	23%	11%	5%	100%		
How often nurses checked on you and how well they kept track of how you were doing.	N	155	137	242	117	49	700	2.67	1.19
	%	22%	20%	35%	17%	7%	100%		
How much nurses ask you what you think is important and give you choices.	N	151	116	233	142	58	700	2.77	1.23
	%	22%	17%	33%	20%	8%	100%		
How the willingness of the nurses to be flexible in meeting your needs.	N	159	130	222	134	55	700	2.71	1.23
	%	23%	19%	32%	19%	8%	100%		
How well they adjusted their schedules to your needs.	N	175	97	152	119	157	700	2.98	1.49
	%	25%	14%	22%	17%	22%	100%		
Ability of the nurses to make you comfortable and reassure you.	N	185	128	242	91	54	700	2.57	1.22
	%	26%	18%	35%	13%	8%	100%		
How quick they were to help.	N	207	149	163	91	90	700	2.58	1.37
	%	30%	21%	23%	13%	13%	100%		
How well things were done, like giving medicine and handling IVs.	N	361	172	88	42	37	700	1.89	1.16
	%	52%	25%	13%	6%	5%	100%		
The teamwork between nurses and other	N	298	169	132	70	31	700	2.10	1.19

hospital staff who took care of you.	%	43%	24%	19%	10%	4%	100%		
Amount of peace and quiet.	N	297	103	73	54	173	700	2.58	1.65
	%	42%	15%	10%	8%	25%	100%		
Provisions for your privacy by nurses.	N	322	117	91	46	124	700	2.33	1.53
	%	46%	17%	13%	7%	18%	100%		
How clearly and completely the nurses told you what to do and what to expect when you left the hospital.	N	191	162	80	111	156	700	2.83	1.53
	%	27%	23%	11%	16%	22%	100%		
Nurses' efforts to provide for your needs after you left the hospital.	N	197	155	83	112	153	700	2.81	1.53
	%	28%	22%	12%	16%	22%	100%		
Overall mean score of the level of patients satisfaction								2.57 (SD = ± 0.877)	40%

Note: *The frequency and percentages are based on n =700. SD: standard deviation. The scoring of the patients satisfaction based on responses of a 5-point Likert-type scale that ranged from one to five (1 = excellent, 2 = very good, 3 = good, 4 = fair, 5 = poor). The total possible scores range from 19–95 points. Lower total scores indicate greater satisfaction with nursing care and higher total scores indicate lower satisfaction with nursing care.

Figure (4.8): The overall level of satisfaction regarding quality of nursing care for surgical patients. (n = 700).

Table (4.2): The relationship between satisfaction level and Sociodemographic data.

The relationship between satisfaction level and demographic data		Excellent		Very good		Good		Fair		Poor		Chi-square P-value
		N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Gender	Male	40	10%	154	40%	121	31%	62	16%	9	2%	0.629
	Female	39	12%	125	40%	98	31%	49	16%	3	1%	
Age in years	18 - 24	22	13%	63	36%	55	31%	31	18%	5	3%	0.260
	25 - 34	13	8%	63	39%	48	30%	32	20%	5	3%	
	35 - 44	17	14%	47	39%	42	35%	14	12%	1	1%	
	45 - 54	12	14%	30	36%	29	35%	11	13%	1	1%	
	55 and above	15	9%	76	48%	45	28%	23	14%	0	0%	
Marital status	Single	15	7%	70	34%	66	32%	46	22%	9	4%	0.001
	Married	57	13%	192	42%	138	31%	62	14%	3	1%	
	Divorced	4	27%	4	27%	5	33%	2	13%	0	0%	
	Widow	3	11%	13	48%	10	37%	1	4%	0	0%	
Occupation	Retired	3	6%	18	33%	14	26%	18	33%	1	2%	0.000
	House wife	28	16%	69	40%	49	29%	25	15%	0	0%	
	Governmental employee	10	12%	42	50%	25	30%	6	7%	1	1%	
	Non-governmental employee	0	0%	3	17%	7	39%	8	44%	0	0%	
	Student	7	9%	47	59%	24	30%	1	1%	0	0%	
	Farmer	13	12%	33	31%	41	38%	19	18%	2	2%	
	Free business	18	10%	66	36%	59	32%	34	18%	8	4%	
Educational level	Illiterate	12	8%	54	36%	53	35%	32	21%	1	1%	0.030
	Khalwa	23	14%	70	44%	38	24%	27	17%	1	1%	
	Primary school	22	16%	45	33%	45	33%	20	15%	5	4%	
	Secondary school	17	11%	60	40%	51	34%	18	12%	3	2%	
	University	5	5%	50	49%	32	31%	14	14%	2	2%	
Residence	Urban	51	15%	155	44%	102	29%	36	10%	6	2%	0.006
	Semi urban	14	7%	73	37%	65	33%	44	22%	3	2%	
	Rural	14	9%	51	34%	51	34%	31	21%	3	2%	
Have you been admitted to the hospital before?	No	51	18%	126	44%	85	30%	21	7%	5	2%	0.000
	Yes for medical reason	9	5%	55	30%	53	29%	61	33%	5	3%	
	Yes for surgical reason	15	12%	44	36%	36	30%	25	20%	2	2%	
	Yes for others	4	4%	54	51%	44	42%	4	4%	0	0%	

4. DISCUSSION:

This study aims to evaluate patient's satisfaction with the quality of nursing care. This study found that the overall satisfaction level of patients receiving nursing care was very good. This could be explained that provision of the quality of nursing care for patients undergone to surgical operations was good. This result agreed to a study conducted at Kenyatta National Hospital on patient satisfaction with nursing care showed that (67.8%) patients were satisfied⁽¹⁴⁾. and similar to a study done by Kebede et al 2022, which reported the total level of satisfaction regarding the quality of nursing care provided was 54.2%⁽¹⁵⁾. On the other hand, the level of satisfaction in this study was higher than in a study conducted at a teaching hospital in Ghana, where about 33% of respondents were very satisfied with their nursing care⁽¹⁴⁾. Furthermore, our the study is similar to a study conducted in Ethiopia by Legesse et al. (J Nurs Care 2016, 5:2), 47% of patients expressed overall satisfaction with nursing care, with a mean satisfaction score of 3.01 and a standard deviation of 0.986⁽¹⁶⁾. on the contrary according to one study (by Abdel Maqsood et al., 2012)⁽¹⁶⁾, patients were less satisfied with nurses' professional knowledge about the disease, health status, investigation results, and prognosis. their illness, and they feel more satisfied with the dedicated care communicate. Özsoy et al.(2007) conducted a meta-analysis⁽¹⁶⁾. This finding was consistent with a study conducted in Iran (58%) and Jimma University Specialized Hospital, Ethiopia (61.9). However, the findings of this study were lower than studies conducted in Australia (69.3), Nigeria (96.1%), and China (80%). The possible justification for this difference might be the difference in the methodology used⁽¹⁷⁾.

Regarding relationship between patients satisfaction and Sociodemographic characteristics. The results of this study showed that, with a 95% confidence level (P value <.05), the satisfaction of participants (marital status, occupation, educational level, residence and, had been admitted to the hospital before). The study showed that patients with lower education levels were more satisfied than those with higher education. This result is similar to studies conducted in Saudi Arabia by Alhowaymel et al(2022), Jordan by Elayan &Ahmad (2018), and Turkey by Karaca & Durna (2019), in contrast with another Saudi study (Al Qahtani & Al Dahi, 2015) and two other studies conducted in Oman by Albashayreh et al (2019) and India by Shinde &

Kapurkar (2014) ⁽³⁾. Other research conducted by (Dzomeku et al., 2013; Geçkil et al., 2008; Milutinovic et al., 2012; Özsoy et al., 2007), literate people and those who completed education primary school expressed greater satisfaction with nursing better service than college or university graduates ⁽⁴⁾. A study conducted in Mukkah Almkarama, reported that as regards participants' educational status, less educated patients have higher satisfaction. 87% of respondents who were illiterate were fully satisfied compared to 56% who had diploma and above; this is similar with the Quinn et al. study in which less educated patients tended to have high satisfaction ⁽¹⁸⁾.

Limitations of the study:

- The convenience sample techniques used in this study prevent the results from being broadly applicable.
- Another limitation of the study was that the sample was limited to surgical patients in selected governmental teaching hospitals in the Darfur region.

CONCLUSION:

According to the finding of the present study, the following can be concluded:

- The overall mean scores of patient satisfaction level regarding the quality of nursing care were highly satisfactory ($M = 2.57$, $SD = \pm 0.877$).
- There is a statistically high significance between the overall mean scores of the patient's satisfaction with sociodemographic characteristics (Marital status, educational level, residence, and previous hospitalization) at p-value ($p < .05$).

RECOMMENDATIONS:

According to the basis of the present study, the following are recommended:

- Further studies should be conducted concerning patient satisfaction with nursing care provided in all hospitals.
- Improving the quality of nursing care should focus more on educating patients when providing quality nursing care.
- Continuous training programs based on evidence-based guidelines will significantly improve the quality of nursing care by establishing continuous professional development programs.

- Hospital authority and nursing administration need to motivate, support, and encourage the nursing staff to attend training programs and workshops related to the quality of nursing care for surgical patients by providing all facilities to them.
- Organizations should consistently include the latest guidelines and standards in their rules, procedures, and instructions to meet their requirements and demands for the universal evolution in nursing care.

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